

SENSITIZATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN IGBO CORE VALUES: A PANACEA FOR THE SOCIAL VICIES IN CONTEMPORARY SOUTH EASTERN GEOGRAPHICAL ZONE OF NIGERIA: A CASE STUDY OF IMO AND EBONYI STATES OF NIGERIA

Anyanele, Silas U. (Ph.D)

Department of Igbo Language and Culture, Federal College of Education, Obudu, Cross River State

Article Details

Volume: 01

Issue: 02

Pages: 12-23.

Month: September

Year: 2025

Recommended Citation for APA 7th Edition:

Anyanele, S.U. (2025). sensitization of secondary school students in Igbo core values: A panacea for the social vices in contemporary South Eastern Geographical Zone of Nigeria: A case study of Imo and Ebonyi States of Nigeria. *International Journal of Premium Advanced Educational Research*, 1(2), 12-23.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Abstract

The study investigated the sensitization of secondary school students in Igbo core values: A panacea for the social vices in contemporary South Eastern Geographical Zone of Nigeria: A case study of Imo and Ebonyi States of Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study and three hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprised all the 158,572 senior secondary class SS 3 students in Imo and Ebonyi States. A sample size of 500 SS 3 students was drawn for the study using a stratified random sampling technique. An instrument titled Impact of Igbo Values Sensitization on Behaviour Assessment Questionnaire (IIVSBAQ) was used for data collection. The face and content validation of the instrument was determined by two experts in the Department of Test, Measurement and Evaluation in the Federal College of Education, Obudu. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded an overall coefficient of 0.728. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and the t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed, among others, that patience and hard work do not impact the behaviours of the Igbo-born students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. It was also found that honesty does impact the behaviours of the Igbo-born students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. Further results indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female students on the impact of patience and honesty on the behaviour of Igbo-born students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the various levels of government in Nigeria, including the Local government, state and federal governments should take the sensitization of our cultural heritages including our core values very serious by making sure that it is studied in all the levels of our educational level up to the tertiary levels, including our polytechnic and monotechnics, to make sure that every child in the school system has a good learning and knowledge of our core values.

Keywords: Sensitization, Students, Igbo, Core values, Social Vices, Patience, Hardwork, Honesty

1.1 Introduction

The importance of bringing up students, especially the secondary school students, in the core values of the society that will help them to behave in the accepted manner of the society, cannot be overemphasized, as the peace and security of the society depend on the positive applications of the core values of the society by the citizens of the society, including the students. Some of the core values that every society needs to inculcate into its members and students include, according to Ajibola (2019), honesty, patience, discipline, respect, kindness, tolerance, forgiveness, justice, sincerity, etc. Unfortunately, most of the students seem not to be abreast of these core values, which underscores the evil manner most of them exhibit in society, which has made society to be messed up with many social vices that are threatening the peace of society, today especially, in the South-Eastern zone of Nigeria and the entire nation in general. The negative behaviours exhibited by contemporary students have left many to question whether the students know that there are core ethical values that control and shape human behaviour in society. Mints (2022) decries the loss of most of society's cherished core values when he writes:

I believe what is missing in society today is the commitment to core ethical values that all people should strive to achieve, such as honesty, kindness, compassion, respect, and personal responsibility. These are values to be admired and illustrative of a person of integrity. Where have they gone? (Page 30).

Lending credence to the position of Mints (2022), Olaitan, Mohammed, Nayaya and Ajibola (2013) noted that:

The indiscipline problem in schools is ranked as a major problem among students of secondary schools in Nigeria. Disruptive behaviour is a concern to schools and parents and to fellow students, whose education may be adversely affected. Therefore, disruptive behaviour cannot be ignored, and schools must tailor a well-understood, sound behaviour and discipline policy. In secondary schools, the situation is worse because the learners are adolescents, now becoming aware of their rights, namely, to privacy, to freedom of religion, belief, opinion, and expression, among others.

Since secondary school students are the hope and future of every society, any laxity or failure in the proper upbringing of the students of any society, especially in the core ethical values, will spell doom for that society. The students of the society need direction; they need to be properly sensitized to the core values of the society to enable them to know the acceptable norms and behaviours of the society and the negative behaviours that the society abhors. It is expected that the 'dos and don'ts' of society be inculcated into the students right from early school days as they grow. Any negligence in this sensitization of the core values spells doom both to the person and society at large. Many factors influence the behaviour and lifestyle of an individual in any given society. Psychologists have advocated that there are two most prominent factors that influence human behaviour, which include biological factors and environmental factors. Biological factors include the traits the person inherited by birth as determined by the genes of the parents and the lineage, while environmental factors include all the experiences the person is exposed to by sight, hearing, touch and physical experience as given to the child by the society. The above theory is

summarized by Cheelee (2019), as he notes that biological factors lay a foundation for us to have the ability to learn, but it is our surroundings and social forces (environmental factors) that lastly determine how we behave.

Karl (2016) agrees with Cheelee that human behaviour is controlled and shaped by the two factors of nature and nurture. Every society owes it a duty to adequately socialize and sensitize its students and youths with the values of the society to enable the students to fit properly in the society when they grow up. In the school system, students need to be properly sensitized, especially in the core values of society, to enable them to fit in and behave in acceptable manners both in the school and out of school. Anyanele (2019) posits that the positive behaviours expected of the members of society are determined by sets of principles called values. Macmillan Dictionary (2019) defines value as the principles and beliefs that influence the behaviour and way of life of a particular group or community. These values act as checks and controls on the lifestyle and behaviours of the citizens of the society, and they help to determine when one is living an anti-societal life or an acceptable life within a given society. A person who lives an acceptable life is said to exhibit positive values, while a person who lives an antisocial life is said to exhibit negative values. This person with negative values has no regard for the norms of society and the person's behaviour will be unacceptable to the members of society as it will be harmful to others.

This implies that there exist in every society, values that act as social control that compel one not to act in manners that will be detrimental to others in the society, or put the society in jeopardy or danger. Human behaviours are exhibited by the application of the values of society to the day-to-day transactions in every aspect of the lives of people. These applications of the values of the society can be positive or negative and affect and influence the peace and well-being of those around the environment they are exhibited. The question of whether the students of the Igbo states of the South East of Nigeria are sensitized to the core values of the Igbo people gave rise to this research, to find out if the students of the areas in question are properly sensitized to the values of the Igbo people.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Accusations have raged on over the years, on whom to blame for the social vices and negative behaviours of the students of Igbo extraction in the South-Eastern states of Nigeria and other parts of our nation. Some of these negative behaviours, also called social vices, include: armed robbery, kidnapping, yahoo yahoo (internet-related frauds), raping, arson, prostitution, exam malpractices in schools, laziness, obtaining by fraud, vehicle snatching, among others. These vices are seen and heard daily in all parts of South-Eastern Nigeria and the entire Nigerian nation at large. There has been blame and counter-blame on who should bear the blame for these vices. Some blame the parents, others the teachers in the school systems, yet others, the government, the society and some the students themselves. As it stands, no empirical study has been carried out to decode the actual person responsible for these anomalies. It seems like scholars have not taken the pain to consider the role of appropriate sensitization of core values of the society on the behaviour of human beings, especially the students. It is also not clear whether the society is adequately sensitizing these students and youths on the values of the society, especially in the early and later school days, beginning from the homes to the schools. It is also not known if these values, which were sensitized, have any impact on the behaviours of the students. The above is the bone of contention of this study. The problem of this study puts in question forms are:

1. Are Igbo secondary school students adequately sensitised to the Igbo core values of Igbo land?

2. What is the impact of adequate Igbo Value Sensitization on the Igbo secondary school students?
3. Can adequate sensitization of Igbo values to Igbo secondary school students be a panacea to the Social Vices currently prevalent in the South-Eastern Geographical Zone of Nigeria?

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of sensitization of Igbo values on Igbo students, as a measure to ameliorate the current social vices in the South-Eastern Geographical Zone of Nigeria. The variables of values that were considered in the study include: patience, hard work and honesty. Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. The impact of patience as one of the Igbo core values, on the behaviours of Igbo-born Students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria
2. The impact of hard work, as one of the Igbo core values, on the behaviours of Igbo-born Students of South South-Eastern geographical one of Nigeria
3. The impact of honesty, as one of Igbo core values on the behaviours of Igbo born Students of South Eastern Geographical Zone of Nigeria.

1.4 Research questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the Study.

1. How does patience, as the Igbo value, impact the behaviours of the Igbo students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?
2. How does hard work, as the Igbo value, impact the behaviours of the Igbo students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?
3. How does honesty as an Igbo value impact the behaviours of the Igbo students of South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female secondary school students on the impact of patience on the behaviours of Igbo secondary school students of South Eastern Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural male and Female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of hard work on the behaviours of Igbo secondary school students of South Eastern Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female secondary school students on the impact of honesty on the behaviours of Igbo secondary school students of South-Eastern Nigeria.

2. Methods

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The area of the study was South South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. The South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria consists of five Igbo-speaking states, which include: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. Only two states, Imo and Ebonyi States, were used for the study as a case study. Imo and Ebonyi states have three senatorial zones each, making a total of six senatorial zones. The population of this study comprises all the 158,571 senior secondary class SS 3 students in Imo and Ebonyi States. Among the population, Imo State has 80,057 SS 3 students and Ebonyi State has 78,514 SS 3 students. A sample size of 500 SS 3 students was drawn for the study using a stratified random sampling technique.

The instrument that was used in this study is a 20-item questionnaire titled Impact of Igbo Values Sensitization on Behaviour Assessment Questionnaire (IIVSBAQ). The respondents are required to indicate on each of the 4 options, the extent to which the sensitization of the selected Igbo values impact on their behaviours namely: to a very great extent (VGE); to a great extent (GE); to a less extent (LE) and to a very less extent (VLE) in secondary schools in Imo and Ebonyi states. The face and content validation of the instrument was determined by two experts in the Department of Test, Measurement and Evaluation in the Federal College of Education, Obudu. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded an overall coefficient of 0.728, which is an indication that the instrument is reliable.

The researcher and four research assistants collected data for the study. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while, t-test was used to test the null hypotheses. In answering the research questions, a mean score of 3.1-4.0 will imply that value sensitization impact to a very great extent on the behaviour of students (VGE); 2.1-3.0 implied that value sensitization impact to a great extent (GE); 1.1-2.0 imply that value sensitization impact to a less extent (LE) and 0.1-1.0 will implied that value sensitization impact to a very less extent (VLE) in behaviours of secondary school students' in Imo State. (Courtesy of Igwe 2011). Standard deviation was used to determine how the responses of the respondents vary. The entire hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance and interpreted thus:

- ❖ Reject HO if f cal is greater than t critical.
- ❖ Accept HO if t cal is less than f critical.

3. Results

Research Question One: How does patience as Igbo value impact on the behaviours of the Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean calculation of impact of patience on the behaviour of Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

S/N	QUESTIONARE ITEMS	VGE	GE	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	S.D	Interpret
1	I have enough patience whenever I am asking for something from my parents	170	125	113	92	2.74	1.11	Accept
2	I do not have patience on making a demand.	79	145	110	166	2.27	1.08	Reject
3.	I do not like wasting my time when I am seeking for something	100	103	143	154	2.29	1.10	Reject
4.	My parents taught me to have patience in everything I am doing	74	96	151	179	2.13	1.06	Reject
5.	I want to get anything I want without wasting time	61	120	124	195	2.09	1.05	Reject
6.	I like doing things quickly quickly	158	129	90	123	2.64	1.16	Accept
7.	No one has taught me to have patience in whatever i am doing.	141	105	80	174	2.46	1.22	Reject
	Average mean					2.37		Accept

Source: Field work 2025

The analysis in table 1, shows that items 1 and item 6 were accepted because their mean is greater than 2.50, while items 2,3,4,5, and 7 were rejected because their mean score is less than

2.50, however, the average mean is 2.37, which is not up to 2.50. From the analysis, those who answered the research questions agreed that patience do not impact on the behaviours of the Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

Research Question Two: How does hardwork as Igbo value impact on the behaviours of the Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean calculation of impact of hardwork on the behaviour of Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

S/N	Questionnaire items	VGE	GE	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	S.D	Interpret
8.	It is difficult for me to read my books	69	96	180	155	2.42	1.22	Reject
9.	I do not work very hard in my father's house							
	I was taught hardwork by my parents.	142	148	104	106	2.65	1.10	Accept
10.	My teachers taught me hard work							
	I frown at work in our house	94	91	145	170	2.21	1.10	Reject
11	I force my younger siblings to do my work for	174	178	71	77	2.89	1.04	Accept
12	me in the house.	72	90	157	181	2.10	1.05	Reject
13	Working is always painful to me in the house							
	and in school.	102	150	173	75	2.55	0.97	Accept
14								
		87	124	179	110	2.37	1.01	Reject
	Average Mean					2.43		Reject

Source: Field work (2025)

The analysis from table 2, shows that items 9, 11 and item 13 were accepted because their mean is greater than 2.50, while items 8, 11, 12 and 14 were rejected because their mean score is less than 2.50, however, the average mean is 2.43, which is not up to 2.50. From the analysis, those who answered the research questions agreed that hardwork do not impact on the behaviours of the Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

Research Question Three: How does honesty as Igbo value impact on the behaviours of the Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean calculation of impact of honesty on the behaviour of Igbo students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria

Source: Fieldwork 2025

S/N	Questionnaire items	VLE	GE	VLE	LE	\bar{x}	S.D	Interpret
15.	I do not cheat in my examinations.	79	124	111	186	2.19		Reject
16.	I often lie when I do something bad	78	239	80	103	2.58		Accept
17.	My parents always flog me when ever							
	I do something bad in the house.	67	223	68	142	2.43		Reject
18	My parents do not punish me when I do bad							
	thing	458	5	15	22	3.79		Accept
19.	I follow my fellow students to tell lie in the							
	school some times.	130	115	73	182	2.38		Reject
20	We were taught not to lie in the church	181	143	97	79	2.85		Accept
	Average Mean					2.70		Accept

The analysis in table 3 above, shows that items 16, 18, and item 20 were accepted because their mean is greater than 2.50, while items 15, 17 and 19 was rejected because their mean score is less than 2.50, however, the average mean is 2.70, and is accepted because, it is more than 2.50. From the analysis, those who answered the research questions agreed that honesty do impact on the behaviours of the Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of patience on the behaviours of Igbo Students of South Eastern Nigeria.

Table 4: t-test analysis of male and female students on the impact of patience on the behaviour of Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

S/N	(Variables)	No	\bar{X}	S.D	DF	t.cal	t.cri	(Decision)	(Significance)
1.	Male	207	2.73	1.12	498	0.12	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)
	Female	293	2.75	1.10					
2.	Male	207	1.59	0.90	498	13.81	1.960	Rej. Ho	(S)
	Female	293	2.75	0.94					
3.	Male	207	2.41	1.14	498	1.92	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)
	Female	293	2.21	1.07					
4.	Male	207	2.27	1.10	498	2.59	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
	Female	293	2.02	1.02					
5.	Male	207	2.21	1.05	498	2.21	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
	Female	293	2.00	1.05					
6.	Male	207	3.09	1.02	498	7.63	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
	Female	293	2.32	1.15					
7.	Male	207	1.76	1.19	498	11.27	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
	Female	293	2.89	1.02					
	T-test		Value			5.65	1.960	Rej.H. O₁	(S)

Source: Field work (2025)

****NS= (Not Significant), S= (Significant)

Analysis in table 4 shows that the t-test calculated is 5.65. It is greater than t-test Critical, which is 1.960. Based on this, hypothesis 1 is rejected. This implies that there is no significance difference

in the mean score of male and female students on the impact of patience on the behaviour of Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural male and Female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of hardwork on the behaviours of Igbo Students of South Eastern Nigeria.

Table 5: t-test analysis of urban and rural male and Female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of hardwork on the behaviours of Igbo students of South Eastern Nigeria

S/N	(Variables)	No	\bar{x}	S.D	DF	t.cal	t.cri	(Decision)	Significance																																																																										
1.	Male	207	1.59	0.98	498	11.43	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)																																																																										
	Female	293	2.61	0.98						2.	Male	207	3.03	0.19	498	9.41	1.960	Rej. Ho	(S)	Female	239	2.26	1.17	3.	Male	207	3.87	0.57	498	12.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	239	3.75	0.76	4.	Male	207	1.76	1.17	498	1.80	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)	Female	293	2.82	1.05	5.	Male	207	1.76	1.07	498	10.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	293	2.82	1.08	6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)	Female	293	2.88	1.08	t.test		Value	
2.	Male	207	3.03	0.19	498	9.41	1.960	Rej. Ho	(S)																																																																										
	Female	239	2.26	1.17						3.	Male	207	3.87	0.57	498	12.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	239	3.75	0.76	4.	Male	207	1.76	1.17	498	1.80	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)	Female	293	2.82	1.05	5.	Male	207	1.76	1.07	498	10.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	293	2.82	1.08	6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)	Female	293	2.88	1.08	t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)								
3.	Male	207	3.87	0.57	498	12.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)																																																																										
	Female	239	3.75	0.76						4.	Male	207	1.76	1.17	498	1.80	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)	Female	293	2.82	1.05	5.	Male	207	1.76	1.07	498	10.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	293	2.82	1.08	6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)	Female	293	2.88	1.08	t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)																						
4.	Male	207	1.76	1.17	498	1.80	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)																																																																										
	Female	293	2.82	1.05						5.	Male	207	1.76	1.07	498	10.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)	Female	293	2.82	1.08	6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)	Female	293	2.88	1.08	t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)																																				
5.	Male	207	1.76	1.07	498	10.61	1.960	Acpt H.O	(NS)																																																																										
	Female	293	2.82	1.08						6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)	Female	293	2.88	1.08	t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)																																																		
6.	Male	207	2.80	1.07	498	0.79	1.960	Accept HO	(NS)																																																																										
	Female	293	2.88	1.08						t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)																																																																
t.test		Value				7.77	1.960	Rej.H.O₃	(S)																																																																										

Source: Field work, 2025

Analysis in table 5 shows that the t-test calculated is 7.77. It is greater than t-test Critical, which is 1.960. Based on this, hypothesis 2 is rejected. This implies that there is a significance difference in the mean score of male and female students on the impact honest on the behaviour of Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of honesty on the behaviours of Igbo Students of South Eastern Nigeria

Table 6: t-test analysis of male and female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of honesty on the behaviours of Igbo Students of South Eastern Nigeria

(Variables)	No	\bar{x}	S.D	DF	t.cal	t.cri	(Decision)	(Significance)
Urban	199	2.75	1.30	498	2.66	1.960	Rej H.O	(S)
Rural	301	3.04	1.15					
Urban	199	3.00	.00	498	4.72	1.960	Rej H.O	(S)
Rural	301	2.62	1.15					
Urban	199	2.98	1.11	498	5.00	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
Rural	301	2.58	1.11					
Urban	199	2.87	1.13	498	11.37	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
Rural	301	3.78	0.63					
Urban	199	2.75	0.95	498	0.11	1.960	Accp H.O	(NS)
Rural	301	2.74	1.01					
Urban	199	2.16	1.09	498	3.29	1.960	Rej.H.O	(S)
Rural	301	2.49	1.10					
Urban	199	1.61	1.03	498	9.08	1.960	Rej H.O	(S)
Rural	301	2.56	1.20					
t-test Value					5.16	1.960	Rej H.O	(S)

Analysis in table 6, shows that the t-test calculated is 5.16. It is greater than t-test Critical, which is 1.960. Based on this, hypothesis 3 is rejected. This implies that there is a no significance difference in the mean score of male and female students on the impact honesty on the behaviour of Igbo born students of South Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria.

4. Discussion of Findings

The analysis in Table 1 shows that items 1 and 6 were accepted because their means are greater than 2.50, while items 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7 were rejected because their mean scores are less than 2.50; however, the average mean is 2.37, which is not above 2.50. In Hypothesis 1, as shown in Table

4, the t-test analysis yields a value of 5.65. It is greater than the t-test critical which is 1.96; hence, hypothesis 1 is rejected.

The findings from table 1 shows that patience, as an Igbo value, do not impact the behaviour of secondary school students. The above findings aligned with the findings of Okoye (2016), who opined that the problem with the present crop of secondary students is a lack of patience to take time and examine issues before acting on them, thereby making serious mistakes that do not give out the required behaviour that society expects. This study has also shown that there is a great deficiency in the attitude of present-day student due to a lack of patience to analyse issues before action.

The analysis in Table 2 shows that items 8, 10 and 12 were accepted because their mean is greater than 2.50, while items 9, 11, 13 and 14 were rejected because their mean score is less than 2.50; however, the average mean is 2.43, which is not up to 2.50. In hypothesis 2, the analysis is in table 5 shows that the t-test calculated is 7.77. It is greater than the t-test Critical value, which is 1.960. Based on this, hypothesis 2 is rejected. The finding from table 2 shows there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of urban and rural male and Female Igbo secondary school students on the impact of hardwork on the behaviours of Igbo-born Students of South-Eastern Nigeria. The findings show that both the students in the rural and urban areas of the states do not work very hard in their studies and other things. The above findings aligned with the findings of Olumba (2015) who decried the lack of hard work seen among students today, especially students in the urban areas, who have so many things that distract them from concentrating in their studies.

The analysis in Table 3 shows that items 16, 18, and 20 were accepted because their mean is greater than 2.50, while items 15, 17 and 19 were rejected because their mean score is less than 2.50; however, the average mean is 2.70, and is accepted because it is more than 2.50. In hypothesis 3, the analysis is in table 6, shows that the t-test calculated is 5.16. It is greater than the t-test Critical value, which is 1.960. Based on this, hypothesis 3 is rejected. This implies that there is a significance difference in the mean score of male and female students on the impact of honesty on the behaviour of Igbo students of the South-Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. This implies that honesty as a value do impact on the behaviour of Igbo-born secondary school students of the Eastern geographical zone of Nigeria. The above findings agreed with the findings of Obot, Abang, Okon and Amalu (2020), whose findings in their study show that honesty can assist in the inculcation of discipline among students. This finding could be explained by the fact that most parents, especially religious parents, teach their children to be honest at all times right from home. Thus, most students already have learnt some degree of honesty before coming to school.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Igbo value do not impact positively on the behaviour of Igbo students. The present crop of Igbo students does not exercise patience in carrying out their duties. Hard work does not exist in current secondary students in the Eastern part of the country. On the other hand, most students are very honest. This is more pronounced in the mission schools where they are taught to be honest in all their doings. Notwithstanding, there is a very urgent need to revisit our cultural values, especially, teaching our students to imbibe them for the peace and progress of the society. Most of the social vices seen today in the Eastern

geographical zone of the country could be reduced if the present students are properly sensitized to the core values of the land. Most students have not even heard about the values of their people, as no one seems to have taught them.

6. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

1. The various levels of government in Nigeria, including the Local government, state and federal governments should take the sensitization of our cultural heritages including our core values very serious by making sure that it is studied in all the levels of our educational level up to the tertiary levels, including our polytechnic and monotechnics, to make sure that every child in the school system has a good learning and knowledge of our core values.
2. The educational administrators in the nation should encourage the study of the Nigerian culture and languages, where the children will be exposed to the core values of each of the ethnic groups in Nigeria.
3. The government should now make it compulsory for every student in the school system must study the Nigerian value system.
4. To preserve our cultural values, cultural education should be included in secondary schools' curriculum and every student should be made to pass it before graduation.

REFERENCES

- Ajibola, S. (2019, August 16). African values and child development. *The Word Magazine*, 3(1), 26-27
- Anyanele, U.S., & Anyanele, C.C. (2015). *An introduction to Igbo history and culture for Igbo second language learners (for schools and college)*. Nsukka: Pascal Communications.
- CheeLee, C.O. (2019). *The Psychological perspective of human behaviour*. Oxford University Press.
- Karl, T.O. (2016). *Nature and nurture explanations of human behaviour*. Cambridge University Press
- Macmillan Dictionary (2019). *Macmillan Dictionary of Contemporary English language*.
- Mintz, U. (2022, Dec. 19). Philosopher of ethics and values in the modern world. *The Classic Magazine* 1(1), 49-50.
- Obot, I.M., Abang, M.A., Okon, A.E., & Amalu, M.N. (2020). Development of honesty and discipline among students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 156(1), 78-82.
- Okoye, J.C. (2016). Problems of Nigerian students' in academic work: A Solution. *The Vanguard Newspapers*. Page. 27.
- Olaitan, T. Mohammed, A., Nayaya, M.O., & Ajibola, A. L. (2013). Management of disciplinary problems in secondary schools: Jalingo Metropolis in focus. *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, 13(14), 7-17.
- Olumba, P.I. (2015). Investigation into students' poor performances in mathematics examinations: A case study of secondary school students of Borki Local Government Area of Cross River State. *An Unpublished N.C.E. Thesis submitted to the School of Education, College of Education, Akamkpa, Cross River State*.